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Gc-Ms Analysis And Antibacterial Activity Of Panchagavya

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Panchagavya is a combined five products of cow (viz., milk, urine, dung, curd, and ghee) used as ancient Indian traditional medicine. And also known as Cowpathy, treating diseases using cow products. Cowpathy (Panchagavya) therapy is an Indian ancient concept in Ayurveda that is concerned with using the components of five cow products for treating various body disorders. The components are obtained from Gas chromatography – Mass spectroscopy analysis. The database was obtained from web sources to identify the components. After analysis of Panchagavya on Gas chromatography – Mass spectroscopy, a total of ten constituents were identified. The antibacterial activity of Panchagavya against two Gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pyogens*) and two Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae*) were analyzed. Panchagavya shows good inhibitory properties on *Staphylococcus aureus* (20 mm) other than all bacteria. The present study showed the components present in Panchagavya and antimicrobial activities.

Keywords: Panchagavya, Staphylococcus aureus, Streptococcus pyogens, E. coli, Klebsiella pneumoniae